

USING LS-DYNA TO SIMULATE THE FORMING OF WOVEN-FABRIC REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Thermostamping of fabrics is a composite manufacturing process that has potential for yielding quality parts with processing costs and time margins that are comparable to the fabrication of stamped metal parts. Researchers have shown that thermostamping of a prepreg fabric can be a cost-effective composites manufacturing process with a cycle time of only seconds [1]. In the current research, LS-DYNA is used to simulate the forming a plain-weave (PW) Twintex® (Fig. 1). Twintex® is made of commingled E-Glass and polypropylene filaments which are woven into conformable fabrics. A hemisphere formed from Twintex® using the thermostamping process is shown in Fig. 2.

The thermostamping process (Fig. 3) for Twintex® starts with the alignment of the fabric in a rigid frame. Multiple layers of fabric are often stamped into one part to achieve the desired part thickness and mechanical properties. The frame and fabric are placed in an oven and are soaked until the fabric reaches a desired temperature for the thermoplastic (polypropylene) fibers to melt. The melting of the polypropylene (PP) fibers infuses the fiberglass fibers and removes the need for a resin infusion step. The frame is then aligned with a punch and die, and binder plates are often used to apply force around the circumference of the part. The application of force by the binder plate induces in-plane forces that can reduce wrinkling of the fabric as it is drawn into the die by the punch. The tools (punch, die and binder plate) are often heated to slow the rate at which the thermoplastic cools. Transfer of the fabric aligned in the frame from the oven to the press is accomplished by moving the fabric holder along shuttle rails. The finished piece assumes the geometry of the die and punch and hardens into a solid part after the thermoplastic has cooled.

Fig. 1. Image of plain-weave Twintex® fabric (left) and schematic of warp/weft layout (right)

Fig. 2. Formed hemisphere made using the thermostamping process

Fig. 3 Schematic example of the thermostamping process

The processing parameters, e.g. the use or nonuse of binders, associated with the thermostamping operation can have a significant effect on part quality. The finite element capabilities of LS-DYNA offer the ability to investigate through simulation how choices in the processing parameters can influence part quality. However, before using LS-DYNA for such an investigation, an understanding of the how the modeling options influence the simulation results must be available to the modeler. The objective of this paper is to explore some of these modeling options.

2 Background

Simulation of the forming process can assist in the design of composites by linking the final form of the composite to be used in service back to the manufacturing process. The simulation of this forming process requires a good understanding of the mechanical behavior of the fabrics. A reliable simulation will help to explore the processing conditions in which the part can be formed without defects, such as wrinkles or tearing, while maintaining a cycle time that is as short as possible. In addition, a simulation tool can provide the orientation of the fabric constituents after thermostamping. This information is of great importance for structural analysis of the formed part. Such structural analyses may include modal analysis, stiffness and damage tolerance. The finite element method is very amenable to the development of a simulation tool for woven-fabric composites because it can account for the mechanical behavior of the fabric and the complex boundary conditions, such as the absence or presence of a binder.

A hybrid finite element discrete mesoscopic approach has been implemented in the commercially available finite element package LS-DYNA to simulate the forming of composite parts using Twintex® woven fabrics. This approach uses beam elements to represent the tensile properties of the yarns and shell elements to represent the shear properties of the dry fabric. This modeling technique captures the evolution of the orientation of the principal load paths as the yarns rotate during the thermostamping process. Fig. 4 shows a unit cell of such a modeling approach for the case of a plain-weave fabric. Details of the beam-shell model are given in [2].

The use of common element types allows this technique to be extended to other widely-used finite

element packages having user-defined material subroutine capabilities, such as Abaqus and ANSYS, without needing special-purpose element types. This approach is appealing to industry because of the direct integration with such commercially available finite element software.

Fig. 4. Plain-weave fabric Unit Cell

3 Material Characterization

The material properties used in the analysis for the Twintex® PW fabric are given in Table 1. Woven fabrics are typically comprised of two sets of yarns intertwined, known as the warp and the weft yarns defined by their orientation. As shown by the schematic in Fig. 1, warp yarns run lengthwise along the fabric, while the weft yarns, also denoted the fill yarns, run from side to side.

Table 1. Twintex® PW material properties

<i>Manufacturer Style</i>	TPEET22XXX
<i>Weave Type</i>	Plain (PW)
<i>Yarn Material</i>	Glass/PP
<i>Area Density</i>	743 g/m ²
<i>Linear Density</i>	1870 tex
<i>Thickness pre consolidation</i>	1.2 mm
<i>Thickness post consolidation</i>	0.5 mm
<i>Yarn Interval [Warp/Weft]</i>	2 mm

For a woven fabric, the two deformation mechanisms at the mesoscopic scale are (1) decrimping (straightening) of the fibers and (2) in-plane shearing of the fabric. The tensile deformation of the yarns is primarily a result of the decrimping. After the yarns have fully extended, then in-plane shearing is the principal mode of deformation during the thermostamping process. The in-plane shearing results in a change of angle between warp and weft yarns and the inter-ply yarn rotations allow the fabric to trellis such that it can

conform to three-dimensional compound-curvature surfaces. It is important to integrate the fabric's measured material properties into the finite element model to generate an accurate forming simulation.

Regressions of experimental data are used to conclude empirical models that are then implemented into the user-defined material subroutines to capture the mechanical behavior of the fabric material in the finite element solver. Finite element models of the various tests are completed to validate that the fabric behavior can be properly simulated using the finite element method.

3.1 Tensile Behavior

In a woven fabric, each yarn passes over and under many yarns, which results in the undulation of the fibers (Fig. 5, top). When a fabric is pulled in the axial direction of the yarns, the deformation of the fabric is composed of two distinct modes. The first deformation mode of the yarn is the tightening of the yarn undulations. After the yarn fully extends, as shown in the bottom of Fig. 5, the second mode of deformation is the axial stretching of the yarns. Therefore, when calculating the properties of the fibers, it is critical to define these two modes of tensile deformation.

Fig. 5. Undulating yarn in woven fabric (top) and fully extended length (bottom)

Uniaxial tensile tests of single yarns were performed on an INSTRON 4464 with a 2-kN load cell. The testing was conducted as directed in the *ASTM D2256 Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Yarns by the Single-Strand Method* [3]. Pneumatic cord and yarn grips were used, and the gauge length was set to be approximately one meter to minimize the effect of the deformation in the grips. The use of a strain gage was not possible due to the specific nature of the tested material. After testing a range of displacement rates between 0.08 mm/s and 8 mm/s,

it was determined that there was no obvious strain-rate dependence over this range, and the displacement rate was set at 5 mm/s for completing the tensile contribution of the material characterization.

The load-displacement data were collected for five samples, and the effective stiffness of the yarns was determined from the slope of the stress-strain curve. The stress-strain behavior of the fabric yarn was fit with a 4th-order polynomial extrapolation while undergoing decrimping, and a linear fit was used after the yarn had reached full extension, as shown in Fig. 6.

A simple finite element model was generated to replicate the tensile test, and a comparison of the simulated results to the experimental data is provided in Fig. 6. The finite element model accurately replicated the experimentally determined results. The good correlation was expected due to the simplicity of the finite element model and the direct integration of tangential modulus into the analysis via a curve fit of the measured tensile data.

Fig. 6. Comparison between experimental and LS-DYNA PW tensile stress vs. true strain

3.2 Shear Behavior

During the thermostamping process, intra-ply shear is the most dominant deformation mechanism undergone by a woven fabric. Therefore, correctly characterizing the intra-ply shear behavior of a woven-fabric is a critical input for accurately modeling the thermostamping process.

The shear frame test, also known as the trellis-frame test and picture-frame test, was used to characterize the in-plane shearing behavior of the fabrics. A general schematic of the shear frame test fixture is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Shear frame test fixture [4]

During the first stages of deformation, the yarns begin to rotate and possibly slip (Fig. 8). Yarn slipping is when two interlaced yarns slide on top of one another. During yarn rotation, it is assumed that the load is initially due to frictional interaction between adjacent yarns at the crossover points. At the deformation state where the yarns can no longer slip against each, adjacent yarn compaction begins to occur (Fig. 8). At this point, adjacent yarns begin to compress each other, resulting in increasing shear stiffness. At a point known as the fabric's locking angle (Fig. 8), the yarns are unable to compact anymore, causing an even steeper increase in shear stiffness. Additional load applied after the locking angle is reached causes out-of-plane deformation, also known as wrinkling. It is at this state of deformation where the highest fabric shear stiffness occurs. After this state is reached, the deformation is governed by a combination of shear, yarn compaction and tension.

Fig. 8. Typical woven-fabric shear behavior [4]

The experimental tests were performed using an INSTRON 4464 and load-displacement data were recorded for analysis. The fabric specimen was sheared at the rate of 0.5 mm/s, and mechanical conditioning, consisting of five pre-test shearing runs, was applied. Ten samples were characterized, five at room temperature and five at the processing temperature of 175°C. The shear stiffness is lower at 175°C due to the reduced shear resistance of the fabric as the polypropylene fibers melt and provide lubrication within the ply.

A shear frame configuration was reproduced in the finite element software, and the simulation results were compared to the experimental data at room temperature (Fig. 9). There is good correlation between the two sets of results, showing that the finite element model can accurately capture the shear behavior of the fabric.

Fig. 9. Comparison of experimental and finite element normalized shear force

3.3 Bias-Extension Behavior

A bias-extension test was performed on an INSTRON 4464 tensile machine equipped with hydraulic grips. Samples of “16 yarns” were used with an aspect ratio of 2:1 between the length and width. The PW fabric samples were 115 mm x 230 mm, and digital image correlation was used to measure the shear angle. The bias-extension experiment consists of a tensile test of the fabric pulled in its bias direction, i.e. the yarns oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the applied load. The typical sample geometry is a rectangular swatch having a length-to-width ratio of 2:1. This geometry leads to a specific strain field involving three different zones with 0° , $\gamma/2$ and γ shearing angles as indicated in Fig. 10.

The bias-extension model was created to confirm that the combined response from shear and tensile forces can be accurately captured by the finite element analysis [5]. A comparison of the load-displacement curves for the plain-weave fabric is shown in Fig. 10. The simulation agrees well with the experimental data up to 30° and then overestimates the load observed from the test. The lower loads of the experiment can be explained by yarn sliding, one physical phenomenon that is not reproducible by the pin-jointed finite element model. In a physical system, the yarns will slide relative to each other within the fabric. However, in the finite element model, a pinned connection is assumed. This pin joint prevents any relative sliding and requires yarn rotation to accommodate the overall fabric deformation in the finite element analysis.

From the good correlation of experimental and simulated results up through 30°, it is concluded that the proposed model accurately captures the fabric behavior during a bias-extension test until the point at which the yarns begin to slide. Thus, the modeling approach is applicable for combined tensile and shear loads.

Fig. 10. Comparison of the load-displacement curves from experimental and simulated bias-extension test

4 Forming Simulations using a Binder

Once it was verified that the fabric behavior was properly represented in the finite element model, a forming simulation was analyzed using the hemisphere geometry. The forming simulation used the plain-weave material model at room temperature and a circular binder ring was applied to tension the yarns during the thermostamping process. The model schematic is shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Part layout for thermostamping model

The forming simulations were not converging to a solution due to high-frequency waves that propagated through the fabric as it came in contact with the punch. The implementation of contact damping was therefore investigated as a means to resolve the convergence issues. Because such parts can be formed using this material system and tooling and if the simulation is to be judged as credible, then the modeling technique should be capable of capturing what physically can be made.

4.1 Contact Damping in LS-DYNA

For forming simulations, 20% of critical viscous damping (VDC) is recommended by LSTC [6] to attenuate the high-frequency dynamics. The hemisphere stamping model with no VDC would only reach 85% completion, while the model with a VDC value of 20 ran to 100% completion. Fig. 12 shows a comparison of the two simulations at 85% completion, where the models have VDC values of 0 and 20, on the left and right, respectively. In the absence of damping, a simulation may give the false impression that out-of-plane wave defects are developed as a consequence of the fabric behavior when subjected to the forming process.

Fig. 12. Comparison between hemispherical stamping part geometry for 0% critical damping (left) and for 20% critical damping (right)

Because this fabric can form a hemisphere without exhibiting the excessive wave displacements as shown in Fig. 12 (right), it is assumed that these out-of-plane wrinkles in the model are a consequence of

the dynamic effects inherent to the numerical method and not a physical phenomenon associated with the fabric. Thus, the use of a nonzero value for VDC is justified if it removes a mechanical behavior of the fabric from the model that does not physically exist. For example, the fabric may naturally dampen such oscillations associated with high-frequency dynamics. Thus, the use of damping must be well characterized by comparing to experimental data before it can be used with confidence in the completion of forming simulations.

Models with VDC values of 5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 25% of critical were analyzed to explore the effect of critical viscous damping on the required punch force. A comparison of the required punch force for various VDC values is shown in Fig. 13, and the differences seen among the three models are insignificant. The maximum percent difference in the punch force between the model with no viscous damping and the six models of varying VCD was 8.57% occurring at 42 mm of punch displacement (70% completion) for 15% of critical damping.

Fig. 13. Comparison of double-dome punch force for varying values of VDC

A comparison of the shear angle contour plots for models where one has VDC=0 and the other has VDC=15 at a punch displacement of 42 mm (70% of simulation completion) is shown in Fig. 14. The contour plots in Fig. 14 indicate that, although there is an 8.57% difference in the punch force as denoted in Fig. 13, the shear angles in both models are essentially the same. The calculation of the shear angle, which is a measure of part quality, is of greater interest than the accuracy of the punch force data. Thus, the use of VDC to eliminate high frequency dynamics within the model does not compromise the intent of the modeling to capture the

final state of fabric deformation which can subsequently be used for structural analyses.

Fig. 14. Shear angle contour comparison between 0 VDC (top) and 15 VDC (bottom) for largest percent difference in punch force at 42 mm of displacement

5 Parametric Studies for “Free” Fabric Forming

For forming simulations that have unrestrained fabric, i.e. no binder, LS-DYNA exhibited difficulties converging to a solution due to wave-like effects in the unclamped region of the fabric or “free” fabric areas. An example of such modeling issues is shown in Fig. 15 for the forming of a double-dome part when not using a binder, i.e. “free” fabric. The “free” fabric hemisphere stamping models experienced the same “wrinkling” issues as the “free” fabric double-dome models. Because this fabric can be formed without a binder, it was speculated that the convergence issues stemmed from inertial effects introduced by the finite element solver.

Inertial effects are a common challenge when using an explicit finite element solver to analyze a relatively “slow” process. The explicit finite element solvers are ideally suited to the investigation of high-speed impact and blast situations. Relative to these situations, the thermostamping of a composite is “slow”. However, the use of an explicit solver for

simulating the forming of a composite is an attractive method because of the robust contact algorithms that are available in the explicit solvers relative to those used in implicit solvers. The numerical methods used in the explicit solvers inherently introduce artificial inertial effects into a “slow” process. Therefore, when using an explicit solver for a “slow” event, modeling options such as mass scaling, time scaling and damping are frequently required to attenuate high-frequency dynamics resulting from the solver.

Fig. 15. Double-dome stamping simulation of “free” fabric just before simulation fails to converge

The following sections discuss the parametric studies completed for this research to explore the benefits and consequences associated with the various modeling options available in LS-DYNA. The geometry chosen for these studies is a double-dome. The double-dome geometry was specifically devised for use in an international benchmarking program for comparing forming simulation results among research groups. The room-temperature plain-weave material model was used for all analyses, and a viscous damping value of 20% of critical, as recommended [6], was used throughout the study.

5.1 Time Scaling in LS-DYNA

In an attempt to resolve the convergence issues associated with inertial effects, time scaling was investigated. The model run time was varied so as to change the effective mass times acceleration experienced by the fabric during the forming process, i.e. time scaling. Table 2 shows that the model end time is inversely related to percent of model completion. By decreasing the model end time by a factor of ten from 0.10 s to 0.01 s, the “free” fabric double-dome model runs to completion and the wrinkling of the free fabric is essentially eliminated.

Table 2. Percent completion of double-dome model for varying model end times

<i>End Time [s]</i>	<i>Percent Completion</i>
0.01	100%
0.02	95%
0.03	85%
0.04	80%
0.05	75%
0.06	65%
0.07	65%
0.08	60%
0.09	55%
0.10	40%

To determine if decreasing the model run time was a viable solution for the stamping of “free” fabric, the models used for material validations, i.e. shear frame and bias-extension tests, were re-run using a reduced end time. Fig. 16 and Fig. 17 compare the experimental shear frame results and bias-extension results, respectively, to the baseline model with an end time of 0.10 s and to the model with an end time of 0.01 s. The results show that decreasing the model end time has adverse effects on the results of both the shear frame and bias-extension models. Thus, time scaling is not a viable modeling option for resolving the waves that are a consequence of the explicit solver.

Fig. 16. Comparison to experimental shear frame results for finite element model end times of 0.1 s and 0.01 s

Fig. 17. Comparison to experimental bias-extension results for finite element model end times of 0.1 s and 0.01 s

Fig. 18. Comparison of shear frame results for an increase in mass by a factor of 100

5.2 Mass Scaling in LS-DYNA

To study the effects of mass scaling on the double-dome model, the mass of the fabric was increased by a factor of 10 and then incremented by 10^{-8} tonne. The results showing how mass scaling influences model completion are presented in Table 3. The model comes closer to completion with increasing mass.

Table 3. Percent completion of double-dome model for varying model mass

$Mass * 10^{-9}$ [tonne]	Percent Completion
1	40%
10	85%
20	90%
30	95%
40	95%
50	100%
60	100%
70	100%
80	100%
90	100%
100	100%

Fig. 19. Comparison of bias-extension results for an increase in mass by a factor of 100

5.3 Global Damping

In another attempt to attenuate the inertial effects of the finite element solver, global damping was investigated. Global damping is a mass weighted nodal damping that applies globally to the nodes of deformable bodies and to the mass center of rigid bodies [7]. This type of damping can be applied to all parts or to a select set of parts. There are two parameters that need to be defined within LS-DYNA to apply global damping: the first is the amount of damping (VALDMP) and the second is to specify the degrees of freedom that damping is applied (STX-SRZ), i.e. any combination of the three translational (STX, STY and SRZ) and three rotational (SRX, SRY and SRZ) degrees of freedom at a node.

Applying global damping to all the parts of a shear-frame model resulted in an increase in the error due to the damping being applied to the rigid frame and

spherical connection joints. Therefore, it was concluded that the global damping would only be a viable option if it was applied exclusively to the fabric, i.e. the deformable beams and shells. The VALDMP values studied for the forming of the double dome are shown in Table 4 along with the corresponding percent of model completion.

Fig. 20 shows the positive z-displacement of the fabric for a forming simulation with VALDMP values of 1E3 and 1E4. The results show that even though a VALDMP of 1E3 gives 100% completion for the double-dome model, it does not prohibit the fabric from lifting off the surface of the die and wrinkling out of plane. Although the fabric may wrinkle during the actual forming process, identifying which modeling parameters minimize the fabric wrinkling is one way to determine a potential set of “free” fabric modeling parameters that can aid in the development of a simulation to correlate well with the physical forming process.

Fig. 20. Comparison of double-dome positive z-displacement contours with VALDAMP values of 1E3 (top) and 1E4 (bottom)

As shown in Fig. 20, the maximum fabric wrinkle height is 5.98 mm and 1.40 mm for global damping values of 1E3 and 1E4, respectively. Therefore, it is concluded that the smallest value of VALDMP to minimize the “free” fabric from lifting off the

surface of the die and eliminate out-of-plane wrinkling is 1E4.

Table 4. Percent completion of double-dome model for varying global damping

VALDMP	Percent Completion
0	40%
1E2	75%
1E3	100%
1E4	100%
1E5	100%

Shear frame and bias-extension models were re-run to study the effects of having a global damping value of 1E4. Fig. 21 and Fig. 22 show how the shear frame and bias-extension results are affected by introducing global damping into the model. The results show that, although the damping value of 1E4 allows the model to run to completion, it significantly over-predicts the force required to shear the fabric. This over-prediction of the shear force will cause discrepancies in the final calculation of the model’s shear angle contour when compared to an experimentally stamped part, and it will also overestimate the stresses in the yarns. As such, global damping is not a viable modeling option.

Fig. 21. Shear frame results with global damping

Fig. 22. Bias-extension results with global damping

5.4 Frequency Range Damping

A study of frequency range damping (FRD) was completed in an effort to resolve the artificial wrinkling that occurs when using an explicit solver for modeling the thermostamping process. Frequency-range damping provides approximately constant damping over a user-specified range of frequencies. There are four user-defined parameters that can be varied in this damping study: (1) the amount of damping in percent of critical (CDAMP), (2) the lower (FLOW) and (3) upper (FHIGH) bounds of the frequency range and (4) which parts are subject to the damping (PSID).

The frequency range damping was applied to the elements that comprise the fabric in the double-dome model. The values studied for frequency range damping and the respective fabric wrinkle heights are summarized in Table 5. All nine variations of frequency-range damping were sufficient to allow the double-dome model to run to completion. However, the fabric wrinkle height changed with the frequency range and the damping values. Table 5 shows that a CDAMP value of 1 is inadequate because it does not sufficiently reduce the fabric wrinkle height. Based on an acceptable wrinkle height of 0.2 mm, set numbers 5 through 9 in Table 5 were chosen for further investigation to determine an acceptable combination of parameters.

Fig. 23 shows the shear frame results for set numbers 5 through 9 in Table 5. The shear frame results for these five sets of frequency range damping parameters are very similar to the baseline response. One conclusion that can be drawn from the results in Fig. 23 is that FRD does not compromise the results for a basic fabric characterization experiment, and, thus it is a potential modeling

option that should be integrated into the forming simulation to prevent fictitious out-of-plane wrinkling that is purely a consequence of the explicit solver. However, it is inconclusive from these runs as to whether or not there is a best choice for a frequency damping range. Therefore, the bias-extension model results were explored to see if the comparison of experimental and model data could assist in choosing the best combination of frequency range damping parameters.

Table 5. Percent completion of double-dome model for varying frequency range damping

Set No.	CDAMP [% critical]	Frequency Range Low [Hz]	Frequency Range High [Hz]	Wrinkle Height [mm]
1	1	5	50	4.16
2	1	50	500	3.47
3	1	500	5000	2.45
4	3	5	50	2.20
5	3	50	500	0.17
6	3	500	5000	0.18
7	5	5	50	0.19
8	5	50	500	0.11
9	5	500	5000	0.08

Fig. 23. Comparison of shear frame results for set numbers 5 through 9

The bias-extension simulation was re-run using the FRD parameters listed in Table 5 for set 5 through set 9. The resulting load-displacement curves are plotted in Fig. 24 alongside the baseline and experimental data. All five of the FRD models correlate well with the experimental and baseline results.

Fig. 24. Comparison of bias-extension results for set numbers 5 through 9

A frequency range between 5 Hz and 50 Hz with a damping value of 5% of critical was chosen as the best set of FRD parameters based on the results shown in Table 5, Fig. 23 and Fig. 24. However, the differences in the results are not significant and, therefore, any of these five sets of frequency range damping parameters can potentially be chosen when modeling the thermostamping of “free” fabric for the double-dome geometry.

Fig. 25 shows the shear angle contour of a completed double-dome stamping model with frequency-range damping applied having parameters FLOW, FHIGH, and CDAMP set to 5, 50, and 5 respectively. The contour plot shown agrees with the expected solution, and there is essentially no out-of-plane wrinkling seen in the simulation.

Fig. 25. Shear angle contour of double-dome stamping model with frequency-range damping

6 Conclusions

A finite element model of the fabric was presented based on the experimentally determined properties. The experiments used to calculate the fabric

properties were modeled in LS-DYNA for validation of the credibility of the material subroutine. The shear frame experimental results were matched in LS-DYNA thereby implying that the shear behavior of the fabric was characterized correctly. The single-yarn tensile experimental results were matched in LS-DYNA thereby implying that the tensile behavior of the fabric was characterized correctly. The bias-extension experimental results were matched in LS-DYNA thereby implying that LS-DYNA was a viable simulation tool for the thermostamping process as it was capable of capturing the combined effects of tension and shear.

Contact damping parameters were studied within LS-DYNA and were selected to allow for a realistic modeling of the excess fabric during the thermostamping process. The implementation of contact damping helps to eliminate some of the high-frequency dynamics associated with the inertial effects that would affect the convergence of the model within LS-DYNA but are not significant during the actual thermostamping process.

A parametric study was completed to determine the best method to model “free” fabric within LS-DYNA. The parameters studied were time scaling, mass scaling, global damping, and frequency range damping. It was determined that frequency range damping not only allowed the most robust modeling of “free” fabric but it also had minimal effects on the shear frame and bias-extension models used for validation. The implementation of frequency range damping within LS-DYNA allowed for not only the stamping of “free” fabric but also a more realistic representation of the compressive behavior of the fabric.

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